

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF *THALICTRUM FOLIOLOSUM* DC. ISOLATION AND CHARACTERISATION OF A NEW ALKALOID, THALICTRINE.

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Berberine and a new quaternary ammonium base, thalictrine, have been obtained from *Thalictrum foliolosum* DC. Thalictrine has been characterised by the preparation of several derivatives.

Thalictrum foliolosum DC. (N.O. *Renunculaceae*; Hindi, Pilihari, Mamiri) occurs in temperate Himalaya and Khasia hills. Its rhizome is considered to be a tonic and laxative and a good substitute for Rhubarb, but it is chiefly used in indigenous medicine as a cheap but valuable substitute for mamira (*Coptis teeta*) in the preparation of collyriums for ophthalmic troubles. Both *Coptis teeta* (Hooper, *Pharm. J.* 1912, 34, iv, 482) and *Thalictrum foliolosum* (Dymock, "Pharmacographia Indica", Vol I, p. 33) are reported to contain large quantities of water-soluble salts of berberine, but as berberine alone could not reasonably account for the beneficial properties attributed to these two drugs, we thought it of interest to make a comparative study of their chemical constituents. The present paper deals with the chemical examination of *Thalictrum foliolosum*, as a result of which the following products have been obtained:

1. Berberine (yield, ca. 0.24% on the weight of the dry powdered drug).

2. A new quaternary ammonium base, $C_{20}H_{27}O_4N$, m.p. 208° , $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +308^\circ$ in 1% aqueous solution (yield, 0.2%), which has been named by us as Thalictrine.

The method of separation of the alkaloids was based on the difference in the solubility of their iodides. Thus, while berberine iodide is insoluble in water, and sparingly soluble in methanol, thalictrine iodide is readily soluble in water and is isolated through its insoluble bismuth double salt. The mother-liquors of berberine iodide (m.p. 260°) gives a yellow coloured iodide melting at 206° . This indicates the presence of yet another base but the quantity of the lower melting iodide is not sufficient for further investigation.

Thalictrine crystallises from dilute methanol with 3 molecules of water of crystallisation which it completely loses in *vacuo* at 100° . Prolonged heating of the dehydrated base at 140° in an atmosphere of hydrogen

darkens the colour but causes no further decrease in its weight. Its quaternary character, established through the analysis of its salts and its inability to add methyl iodide, is not affected by heating under conditions mentioned above. Thalictrine contains two methoxyls, one *N*-methyl and two olefine double bonds, deduced from its behaviour towards bromine in the cold. These findings suggested that thalictrine might be derived from a hexahydro product of berberine, in which the nitrogen ring is reduced. The presence of a phenolic hydroxyl is indicated in thalictrine through intense brown-violet colouration with ferric chloride and the absence of methylene oxide and methyl groups is shown by a negative phloroglucinol-sulphuric acid reaction and a negative side-chain methyl value. In view of all these facts thalictrine has been tentatively assigned the structure (I) to show its probable genetic connection with berberine, the main alkaloid of this plant.

In the course of this investigation it has also been noted that the rhizome of *thalictrum foliolosum* is appreciably hygroscopic in character and does not stock well. After about six months' keeping of the same sample, the yield of crystalline berberine hydro-iodide was reduced to nearly a quarter, while thalictrine could be obtained only in traces. An examination of the pharmacological action of thalictrine is projected.

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

A fresh supply of the drug was obtained from the Himalayan Drug Company, Dehra Dun. It was identified by Messrs. N. L. Bor and C. E. Parkinson, Botanists, Forest Research Institute, Dehra Dun, and also by the Superintendent, Royal Botanic Garden, Sibpur, Calcutta, to whom the authors' sincerest thanks are due.

A fat-free sample of the drug powder gave on complete ignition 5% of ash, which showed the presence of iron, calcium, magnesium, potassium, phosphate, carbonate, and traces of sulphate and halogen.

After a series of preliminary experiments 2 kg. of well-powdered rhizome were percolated 3 times in the cold with methanol. The combined percolates (about 4 litres) were concentrated below 45° in *vacuo* to a soft extract, which was of a yellowish brown colour. This was taken up in about 500 c.c. of water and shaken out with ether (1 litre) to separate the fatty fraction.

Separation of Berberine and Thalictrine.

The yellowish brown aqueous solution from above was treated with potassium iodide, and the heavy yellowish precipitate was filtered and well washed with water. The precipitate weighed 12 g. after drying on a porous plate. The methanol-insoluble portion of this iodide gave 6 g. of berberine iodide (m.p. 260°) after purification through 10% acetic acid and alcoholic hydrochloric acid.

The combined aqueous filtrate and washings from the original iodide precipitate were treated with an excess of Dragendorff's reagent, and the bismuth double salt precipitate was sucked and successively washed with water, alcohol and finally some ether. The dry powder was then suspended in 50% dilute methanol and treated with an excess of freshly precipitated silver hydroxide, filtered and repeatedly washed with hot dilute methanol and finally with water. The black residue was rejected and the methanol-water extracts were carefully concentrated till nearly free from the solvent. The pasty concentrate was then extracted with methanol and the methanol solution treated with ether and a little petroleum ether which removed dark reddish impurities, leaving a nearly colourless solution from which thalictrine crystallised out in the cold as stars of needles. After repeated crystallisations from methanol the base finally melted at 208°, subsequent recrystallisation leaving the m.p. unaltered (yield, 4 g.).

The dark coloured methanol extract (125 c.c.) from the total iodide precipitate, obtained at the outset, was treated with ether and petroleum ether. The reddish yellow filtrate from the dark brown oily precipitate gave a yellow coloured iodide, which melted at 206° (as against berberine iodide melting at 260° and thalictrine iodide melting at 265°), was insoluble in water and thus appeared to be the iodide of a base different from both berberine and thalictrine. The rest of the methanol extract as also the acetic acid and the alcoholic hydrochloric acid extracts from the initial iodide precipitate appeared to consist of mixtures of the iodides of the three bases and were not pursued further.

Characterisation of Thalictrine.

Thalictrine, $C_{20}H_{27}O_4N$, $C_{17}H_{18}(OH)(OMe)_2$, $NMe(OH)$, crystallises from dilute alcohol with three molecules of water of crystallisation, m.p. 208° . On drying to constant weight in *vacuo* at 100° over P_2O_5 , the air-dried crystals lost 13.6% of their weight. $C_{20}H_{27}O_4N, 3H_2O$ requires H_2O , 13.5%. (Found in the air-dried sample : C, 60.8; H, 8.2, $C_{20}H_{27}O_4N, 3H_2O$ requires C, 60.2; H, 8.3 per cent). As obtained after drying to constant weight at 100° , thalictrine forms a white crystalline powder which begins to shrink with darkening from 190° onwards, melts down giving a meniscus at 223° and decomposes at $224-25^\circ$. The dehydrated base suffers no further loss in weight when kept at 140° for 3 hours in an atmosphere of hydrogen. It is easily soluble in water and alcohol but sparingly so in dry benzene, acetone, ether and petroleum ether and shows $[\alpha]_D^{24} = +370^\circ$, as against $[\alpha]_D^{24} = +308^\circ$ for thalictrine containing 3 molecules of water of crystallisation. The free base deteriorates on stocking and absorbs atmospheric carbon dioxide. (Found in dehydrated base : C, 69.8, 70.11; H, 7.01, 7.7; N, 4.1, 4.5. $C_{20}H_{27}O_4N$ requires C, 69.6; H, 7.8, N, 4.1 per cent). Thalictrine gave a negative value in the $CH_3(C)$ determination.

Determination of OMe and NMe (Zeisel, Herzig and Meyer's methods) showed the presence of 2(OMe) and 1(NMe). [Found in dehydrated base; OMe, 18.06; NMe, 5.16. $C_{20}H_{27}O_4N$ requires (for 2OMe) OMe, 18.02 and (for 1 NMe)Me, 4.4 per cent].

Thalictrine decolourises acidified potassium permanganate solution without showing any fluorescence and does not form an insoluble compound with acetone. In concentrated sulphuric acid the base dissolves with a pinkish colour which changes through reddish violet to bluish violet. The blue tinge deepens on standing. Drops of water lighten the colour and further dilution gives a reddish yellow solution. In concentrated nitric acid it dissolves with an orange-red colour which fades down to straw yellow on warming. Dilute nitric acid dissolves it with a deep red colour. Chlorine water when added to an aqueous solution of its hydrochloride gives an immediate deep red colouration which lightens on standing.

Thalictrine chloride came out on adding ether and petroleum ether to a concentrated solution of the base in alcoholic hydrochloric acid as an oil, which when washed repeatedly with ether and evacuated, formed a white hygroscopic powder. It softens from 161° onwards and froths up at $163-65^\circ$. (Found after drying to constant weight at ordinary temperature : Cl, 10.2. $C_{20}H_{26}O_3N Cl$ requires Cl, 9.8 per cent).

Thalictrine chloroplatinate was obtained by adding a 5% solution of platinic chloride to a solution of the chloride as a pale yellow precipitate which after washing and drying in *vacuo* became nearly colourless. It begins to darken from 215° onwards, swells at 231° and decomposes at 233-34°. [Found : Pt, 17.3. $(C_{20}H_{22}O_2N Cl)_2$, $PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 18.3 per cent].

Thalictrine iodide was prepared by bringing together the components in absolute alcohol medium. Crystallised from a mixture of alcohol, acetone and ether it was obtained as a light cream-coloured powder, easily soluble in water and alcohol, m.p. 265° (decomp.). (Found after drying to constant weight at 100°. I, 27.8. $C_{20}H_{22}O_2NI$ requires I, 27.9 per cent).

Thalictrine picrate was obtained by adding aqueous picric acid to an aqueous solution of the base. On recrystallisation from methanol it formed aggregates of stout, spike shaped, bright yellow needles, fairly soluble in hot alcohol, sparingly so in water and melting at 207-8°.

Tetrabromothalictrine acetate.—To the base (0.15 g.) in glacial acetic acid (5 c.c.) was slowly added 1% solution of bromine in the same solvent (equiv. to 4 Br) with ice-cooling. In the beginning every fresh addition produced a yellow thread-like precipitate which dissolved on shaking, giving a yellow tinge to the solution, but on further addition a permanent granular yellow precipitate settled down. This was filtered, well washed with ether and dried on a porous plate. From the ethereal washings a further quantity of the bromo product crystallised out in stars of orange-coloured needles. The bromo derivative is soluble in alcohol and water, sparingly soluble in chloroform, ethyl acetate and glacial acetic acid, and insoluble in ether. It begins to blacken and shrink from 200° onwards and decomposes with frothing at 248-50°. (Found after drying to constant weight at 100° over P_2O_5 : Br, 46.4. $C_{22}H_{20}O_2NBr_4$ requires Br, 45.3 per cent).

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